

D8.1: EOSC Web Portal (initial version)

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Status	Final
Version	V1.10
Date	13/03/2017

Dissemination Level

- PU: Public
 PP: Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission)
 RE: Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission)
 CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission)

Abstract:

This document contains a description of the EOSCpilot website, which has been launched in M2, February 2017. The website is available at: www.eoscpilot.eu and it is maintained by the task leaders of subtask 8.2.1, Web portal & Branding, TRUST-IT.

The document also outlines the internal web platform and mailing lists, used by the consortium members to communicate and manage project documentation.

The European Open Science Cloud for Research pilot project (EOSCpilot) is funded by the European Commission, DG Research & Innovation under contract no. 739563

Document identifier: EOSCpilot –WP8-D8.1	
Deliverable lead	TRUST-IT
Related work package	WP8
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Due date	28/02/2017
Actual submission date	27/02/2017 (date of web site launch)
Reviewed by	
Approved by	
Start date of Project	01/01/2017
Duration	24 months

Versioning and contribution history

Version	Date	Authors	Notes
0.1	06/03/2017	TRUST-IT	First Draft
0.2	13/02/2017	TRUST-IT	Internal revisions

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INTRODUCTION

Under the set of activities planned in Work Package 8, a specific subtask for the development and the maintenance of the EOSCpilot website has been set up.

As outlined in the objectives described in the Description of Work, the EOSCpilot public website was launched in February 2017 - M2, following suggestions and requirements gathered from the other partners involved in the project that have been contributing on and provided feedback to the 8.2.1 task leaders (TRUST-IT).

The website developed for EOSCpilot project features a public website and an internal communication platform.

The public website is accessible to all users visiting www.eoscpilot.eu, and it was launched at the end of February (M2); it is described in details in Public Website section.

An Internal Communication Platform, based on different open source systems (shown in section 3.2), has been developed in order to support the communication among partners and third parties involved in the project; this area has been described in details in Internal communication Platform section and includes the set up and management of the project **mailing** lists.

In addition to the web-based platforms, the same task is responsible for the design and implementation of the overall **graphic design and EOSCpilot branding** (outlined in Section 2)

1. OBJECTIVES AND OVERVIEW

Two main objectives were addressed in WP8, subtask 8.2.1, regarding the development of an EOscpilot website and branding:

- **Design, development and management of an EOsc Pilot web portal** for project promotion and awareness raising as well as a set of collaborative communication tools for project partners (intranet, mailing lists, wikis, etc.).
- **Design and delivery of the EOscpilot branding & graphic design package** covering a series of communication materials, templates, stylesheets and GUIs for the service portfolio. It will also ensure consistent graphic design across all WPs for their interaction with stakeholders, for example, the creation of specific presentation packages for policymakers, service-providers, in order to create a suite of dissemination & communication tools.

Four other specific objectives regarding EOscpilot website addressed in the description of work are:

- **Promote EOsc information** with clear and simple messaging that leaves no room for ambiguity. Having worked extensively with SMEs and representative bodies representative of EU28, the communication partners will create the appropriate message for the stakeholder being addressed. Citizens also need dedicated guides as they have different information needs based on geographical location in EU28 and per demographic.
- Ensure **enhanced user experience from the 15 science demonstrator pilots** through informative and practical services and tools.
- Showcase **EOsc standards and guidelines** for service providers to follow.
- Be the central point to **aggregate the science demonstrator pilot users** to the targeted **workshops** and to the **events**, to register and to build the community.

A set of specific KPIs have been established regarding the full deployment and exploitation of the online website (Table 1).

KPI	Measure
Number of visitors	At least 1000/month by the end of the project
Landing pages	Each relevant topic (events, features, releases, etc.) must have a dedicated page

Table 1 – EOscpilot website KPIs

2. BRANDING

EOSCpilot original branding has been designed to express the project's core mission.

Figure 1 – EOSCpilot logo, version 1 (full version)

Figure 2 – EOSCpilot logo, version 2 (no-payoff)

Figure 3 – EOSCpilot logo, version 3 (B&W version)

The logo uses shades of blue colours and a design that wants to represent the complexity of Europe's network in terms of data connections and infrastructures.

The logo has already been used for project templates for PowerPoint presentations, document files, project's website, all social media platforms and press releases.

Branding activity for EOSCpilot includes the creation of a variety of graphic material, to be used on the website pages in order to foster the user experience and the impact of the platform, on social media channels and in all other communication and dissemination outputs that will be delivered during the project life span.

Figure 4 and Figure 5 show two examples of the collateral graphic material developed for EOSCpilot.

Figure 4 – EOSCpilot banner, n.1

Figure 5 –EOSCpilot banner, n.2

The EOSCpilot logo was the starting point for the design and style of the public web site (described in the sections below).

3. WEBSITE

During the first two months of the EOscpilot a first iteration of the project's website has been developed, consisting in a design-oriented, fully-responsive platform on which information on the EOscpilot project are displayed in relation to the status of work and activities conducted so far.

In order to meet the objectives outlined, the EOscpilot website has been developed following a specific structure and integrated with different features, combining communication and technical aspects.

Figure 6 – EOscpilot website architecture

3.1. Public Website

The public website intends to provide an overview of the EOscpilot project available to the wide audience, an introduction to the specific project objectives, information on the consortium partners and third parties, a constant and reliable source for any update regarding EOscpilot project activities, an overview on the **Science Demonstrators** and other Service and Architecture activities planned. It acts as the reference platform for any communication and request for information coming from EOscpilot stakeholders.

The adopted infrastructure solution is Drupal, a powerful open source platform that allows creating flexible content, integrating new website features easily and developing an innovative and efficient user experience.

3.1.1. Current version

A first website iteration, launched at M2, has been carefully developed and tailored on the basis of EOscpilot needs, taking into account both the graphical and the technical requirements for future developments.

The details of the different sections available in the website so far are listed in the following sections.

Figure 7 – EOscpilot public website sitemap

3.1.1.1. Home page

The homepage of the first iteration of EOscpilot website provides an exhaustive overview on the project vision and goals, at the same time offering a first version of the content that will be further developed during the coming months.

The home page currently features:

- *An interactive slider*: providing a first impact for the user on EOscpilot project and acting as a useful feature for highlighting specific content.
- *EOscpilot Building Blocks*: providing a first comprehensive description of the four different pillars upon which EOscpilot will develop its activities.
- *EOscpilot Mission*: with a bullet list providing instant understanding of the values and goals of the project.
- *Who can benefit from EOscpilot*: where all project stakeholders are displayed graphically. In the second iteration, each stakeholder icon will be clickable and it will link to a dedicated page.
- *Events*: an highlight on the major forthcoming events; it will lead to the events section.
- *News & Publications*: showing the latest news and articles uploaded regarding EOscpilot and other relevant activities.
- *Join our community*: the section acts as the first contact point for the user, who can here:
 - Subscribe to the newsletter
 - Submit a newspiece for publication
 - Submit an event to be added to the web site
- *Social Media*: linking to the Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of EOscpilot
- *Privacy*: providing the terms & conditions for the website registration, personal data management and access, copyright and other legal information.
- *Contact*: linking to a specific contact form where the user can simply fill the required fields and contact EOscpilot team

Figure 8 – EOSCpilot home page (27 Feb 2017)

3.1.1.2. About

The about section is providing an overview on the project main objectives and specific objectives, as well as a short description on the overall numbers (i.e. 9 work packages, 28 milestones, 33 partners, etc.).

When possible, the content uploaded are supported by infographics, charts and banners, trying to provide a easier comprehension of EOSC to the users navigating on the website.

EOSCpilot Objectives:

The EOSCpilot project will support the first phase in the development of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC), as described in the EC Communication on European Cloud Initiatives:

- establishing the governance framework for the EOSC and contribute to the development of European open science policy and best practice;
- developing a number of demonstrators functioning as high-profile pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to show interoperability and its benefits in a number of scientific domains; and
- engaging with a broad range of stakeholders, crossing borders and communities, to build the trust and skills required for adoption of an open approach to scientific research.

These actions will build on and leverage already available resources and capabilities from research infrastructure and e-infrastructure organisations to maximise their use across the research community.

- Reduce fragmentation between data infrastructures by working across scientific and economic domains, countries and governance models, and
- improve interoperability between data infrastructures by progressing and demonstrating how data and resources can be shared even when they are large and complex and in varied formats.

The EOSCpilot project will improve the ability to preserve and reuse data resources and provide an important step towards building a dependable open innovation environment where data from publicly funded research is always open and there are clear incentives and rewards for the sharing of data and resources.

Interaction with the EOSC:

Science Demonstrators Objective
To develop a number of Science Demonstrators in particular domains that will show the relevance and usefulness of the EOSC Services and their enabling of data reuse, and will drive the further development of the EOSC.

Services Objective
To create a number of EOSC pilot services that federate data, infrastructure and services fostering multidisciplinary research across geographical borders and across time (through data preservation).

Interoperability Objective
To define and implement specifications, interfaces, standards and processes that enable and underpin interoperability and sharing of EOSC data and infrastructures across disciplines and providers.

Skills Objective
To develop common standards and assessment frameworks to ensure that organisations and individuals are motivated to develop the capabilities and competencies that the EOSC will rely on, and to develop an EOSC education and training strategy and coordinate its delivery.

Community Engagement Objective
To identify and bring together, through an effective engagement and communication strategy plan, the major groups of stakeholders from the scientific research, private and public sectors coupled with supporting the project through an effective communication and outreach strategy based around results oriented content.

Management Objective
To establish an effective and efficient collaboration between the partners creating added value through shared research and innovation activities to deliver the objectives of the project.

Who is involved?

EOSCpilot in Numbers

- 9.95 M€
- 33 Partners
- 24 Months
- 1035 Person-months
- 1 Coordinator (STFC)
- 9 Work Packages
- 28 Milestones
- 50 Deliverables

The EOSCpilot project gathers a consortium of 33 pan-European organisations & 15 third parties covering a range of disciplines and organisations working together to develop a European-wide governance framework for a pan-European "trusted virtual environment with free, open and seamless services for data storage, management, analysis, sharing and re-use, across disciplines".
To learn more about the organisations contributing to EOSCpilot, visit [Consortium](#)

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PRIVACY CONTACT

Figure 9 – About page

3.1.1.2.1. Consortium

On the consortium web page, all the project partners and third parties currently involved in EOSCpilot project are listed, with the logo and the URL of their website.

The screenshot shows the 'Consortium' page of the EOSCpilot web portal. The page is divided into two main sections: 'EOSCpilot Consortium' and 'EOSCpilot Third Parties'. Both sections feature a table with columns for 'Logo', 'Name', and 'Country'. The 'EOSCpilot Consortium' table lists 30 organizations, including Science & Technology Facilities Council (UK), DOE Office of Biological and Environmental Research (US), EMBL (DE), SURF SARA (NL), GSI (DE), Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (FR), The University of Hamburg (DE), STFC (UK), PSI (CH), Jisc (UK), FAIR (UK), COSMIC (UK), INFN (IT), DESY (DE), STFC (UK), ECRIN (FR), PIN (UK), and CINECA (IT). The 'EOSCpilot Third Parties' table lists 15 organizations, including the Helmholtz Society of Germany and Forschungszentrum Jülich (DE), Nijmegen (NL), University of Cologne (DE), Fraunhofer (DE), GENCI (FR), CRCS (FR), University of Mainz (DE), POND (FR), Institut Teknologi Sepuluh Nopember (ID), GEANT (EU), GRIAT (NL), Consortium GARR (IT), PSNC (UK), and RENATER (FR). To the right of the consortium list, there is a 'NEWS & PUBLICATIONS' section with several news items dated from 2017, such as 'THE EOSCPILOT PUBLIC WEBSITE IS ONLINE' and 'RELAUNCHING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD'.

Figure 10 – Consortium page

3.1.1.3. Science Demonstrator

As science demonstrators have crucial importance for EOSCPilot development, a specific section on the website was created, collecting the science demos available so far.

A first, introductory landing page is showing which type of science demonstrator EOSCPilot develops and in which particular domains.

On the right side, the column is showing all the links to the science demos pages available at the moment.

Figure 11 – Science Demonstrators page

3.1.1.4. News & publications

The news and publications section highlights all the relevant updates regarding EOSCpilot project and community, as well as listing all the relevant publications that have been published on other platforms.

Figure 12 – News & publications page

3.1.1.5. Events

The events page lists all the EOSCPilot events, third parties events and relevant events. The EOSCPilot events section is currently not visible as there are no events listed for the moment.

Figure 13 – Events page

3.1.2. Future Plans

The public website will evolve and address continuous developments, according to the project outcomes and requirements that will emerge during the 24-month lifetime of the project.

Science demonstrator area: The current section will be expanded and further integrated with the application process, and with the information and results coming from the applications themselves. In details, this implementation mainly cover:

- A **dedicated area on the website**, describing how the submission works and all the information needed;
- An online **submission** form / or an alternative submission process;
- A **graphic box on the homepage**, highlighting the submission;
- **Integration** of the submitted proposals in the EOSCpilot database.

Stakeholders: Another forthcoming implementation will cover the integration of the stakeholders section into the website, providing a deeper overview on each stakeholder outlined in home page.

Home page new section: the homepage will be harmonized with a graphic banner, which will be positioned before the stakeholder section. The banner will display Europe's research infrastructure challenges and current needs, together with the aims and the goals of EOSCpilot.

Newsletter: in order to deliver monthly EOSCpilot internal ("The EOSCpilot Insider") and external Newsletters ("The EOSCpilot Scoops"), a forthcoming implementation will also include the integration with Simplenews by Drupal. The system presents many features, among which it will allow to:

- Send newsletters to lists of subscribers;
- Allows both anonymous and authenticated users to opt-in to different mailing lists;
- Have multiple newsletter categories with separate settings;
- Customizable newsletter templates.

Events: the events area will be further implemented, integrating it with an automated chronological order and archiving, thus providing an improved user experience. The area will be incorporated with another subsection, the EOSCpilot Events, in which all events directly organised and managed by EOSCpilot will be displayed.

The implementations listed above represent just a sample of what is being planned for future developments, as these may involve other features or modifications depending on the project needs that will emerge over the following months.

3.2. Internal communication Platform

The aim of having an internal communication platform is to make it easy for all the people working to have a virtual area where to easily access to all project data and to interact with each other, in the most efficient way.

3.2.1. Current version

The platform has been built upon three elements, which are: an Intranet area, an integrated mailing lists and a File repository.

Figure 14 – Internal Communication Platform structure

3.2.1.1. Intranet

EOSCpilot Intranet, based on Organic Groups by Drupal, has been implemented in order to support all the communication among members and third parties regarding the project activities.

A first iteration of the Intranet section has been developed, featuring some components that allow interacting and exploiting the platform for the initial phase of activities.

At the moment, the Intranet area features:

- **Groups and membership** subscription;
- **Landing page** with all groups available and their active members already subscribed;
- A **Communication area**, with a toolkit, an events calendar and an internal newsletter page where all members can independently insert their WP updates;
- **Wiki pages**, which each user can easily create and tailor based on the group's needs;
- Integration and direct linking with the **File Repository**;
- Integration with the **Mailing lists** system.

Each registration request is being accepted after careful analysis, in order to guarantee data privacy and data protection on all the information and documents stored on EOSCpilot Intranet.

Each message sent to the group page, is automatically sent to the entire mailing list, and it thus remains archived on the Intranet.

Welcome to the EOscpilot INTRANET! Click on each mailing list title to see the group activity.

Admin
Admin & Financial Contacts for each partner
[CONTINUE READING](#)

Consortium
Read & manage conversations regarding the EOscpilot consortium
[CONTINUE READING](#)

EAB - External Advisory Board
Read & manage conversations regarding the External Advisory Board
[CONTINUE READING](#)

GA - General Assembly
Read & manage conversations regarding the General Assembly
[CONTINUE READING](#)

PCO - Project Coordination Office
If you are the Project Coordination Officer or you are allowed to access, here you can manage your communication within the group.
[CONTINUE READING](#)

SB - Science Board
Read & manage conversations regarding the Science Board
[CONTINUE READING](#)

Find and manage all the EOscpilot documents and files in the 'NewCloud' repository.

File Repository

Communication
[Newsletter](#)
[Events Calendar](#)
[Internal Newsletter](#)

Recent Activity
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Donatella Castell On 06 March 2017
Draft questionnaire: stakeholder contribution to Governance Development Forum
By Saara Varto On 06 March 2017
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Per Olof On 06 March 2017
Kind Reminder: Mini survey to identify EOsc stakeholders for engagement, communication and skills development (WPTB)
By Vasso Kalatzi On 06 March 2017
Notes from call on EOsc17
By Angus Whyte On 06 March 2017
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Matthew Scott On 06 March 2017
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Fabio Pagan On 06 March 2017
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Volker Beckmann On 06 March 2017
Re: [pco] EOscpilot Nominations for Science Board
By Volker Beckmann On 06 March 2017

NEWS & PUBLICATIONS
22 February 2017
THE EOscPILOT PUBLIC WEBSITE IS ONLINE!
The EOscpilot website is officially online!
24 February 2017
REALISING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD
In October 2016, the first report and recommendations of the Commission High Level Expert Group on the European Open Science Cloud were published.
24 February 2017
EOscPILOT: GETTING THE EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD OFF THE GROUND

Figure 15 – Intranet home page

3.2.1.2. Integrated Mailing Lists

The mailing lists have been developed on Organic Groups and they have been fully integrated into the EOscpilot Intranet. Each subscribed member is able to easily communicate to her/his group members and keep track of all messages (and their attachments), which are stored on the group area, inside the Intranet.

3.2.1.3. File Repository

The file repository is based on the OwnCloud system. It is a user-friendly file repository that allows users to:

- Upload files
- Create folders
- Share documents/folders

With this system, all users can share, store and download all project's files and documents, like:

- Project documentation
- Communication toolkits
- Deliverables
- Milestones

OwnCloud is a self-hosted file sync and share server which you can access through a web interface. It is organised following the WPs structure of the project and the project management organisation.

The File Repository has been completely integrated with the Intranet area, as the access rights (and the credentials) that each user has on the Intranet, are reflected on the File Repository. In order to foster the transparency of data among members, all the users have read/write access to all areas, a part from the PCO folder. As the project coordinator, STFC has a super admin role and has exclusive access rights to the Project Coordination Office (PCO) folder.

Name	Size	Modified
WP6 - EOsc Interoperability	14.2 MB	8 hours ago
WP8 - Engagement and Communication	5 MB	3 days ago
WP2 - Governance	11.9 MB	4 days ago
EXC - Executive Committee	3.6 MB	4 days ago
WP1 - Management	133 KB	7 days ago
Communication Toolkit	29.8 MB	7 days ago
WP4 - Science Demonstrators	697 KB	10 days ago
WP5 - Services	12.1 MB	13 days ago
Project meetings	112 MB	20 days ago
WP3 - Policy	0 KB	25 days ago
Admin	0 KB	a month ago
Consortium	0 KB	a month ago
SB - Science Board	0 KB	a month ago
GA - General Assembly	0 KB	a month ago

Figure 16 – File Repository

3.2.2. Future Plans

A forthcoming implementation that is currently under development is the **online calendar** – an up-to-date, online and accessible calendar on which each user/team member/WP leader could insert events, deadlines, conference-calls and so on. This will allow all members to be aligned on the activities, just accessing to the Intranet.

Moreover, another forthcoming feature that will be implemented on the Internal Communication Platform is an internal **Web conference Tool**, based on BigBlueButton system. This tool will be completely integrated into the Intranet area of EOscpilot and will allow each member to use this as the official tool for managing meetings and online conferences.

The Internal Communication Platform is continuously being implemented and it will be further developed, also on the basis of the different needs that will rise during the following 24 months of activities.

ANNEX A. GLOSSARY

Term	Explanation
PCO	Project Coordination Office
WP	Work package